

ClairCity: Citizen-led air pollution reduction in cities

D2.6 ClairCity Annual Conference – Portugal

April 2019 (revised November 2019)

Document Details

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Description	<p>This report provides evidence that the ClairCity Annual Conference 2019 (externally facing, public event) has been implemented successfully.</p> <p>The Conference was held on the last day of the 3-day ClairCity Annual Consortium Meeting which took place on 8-10 April 2019. The conference was well-attended by over 60 external people which included high-level politicians, NGOs and university and school staff and students.</p> <p>This report includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- A copy of the three-day programme- An overview of participants- References to the public relations around the conference

Version History

Version	Updated By	Date	Changes / Comments
V1.0	Irati Artola	April 2019	Initiating document
V2.0	Corra Boushel	April 2019	Contributions to document
V3.0	Irati Artola	November 2019	Revision of deliverable

Contributions and Acknowledgements

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Native Language Check	Corra Boushel (UWE)
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1 Introduction

This report provides evidence that the ClairCity Annual Conference 2019 (externally facing, public event) has been implemented successfully.

The Conference (externally facing, public event) was held on the last day of the 3-day ClairCity Annual Consortium Meeting which took place on 8-10 April 2019 in Aveiro, Portugal.

ClairCity project partners and External Advisory Board members spent two days (8 & 9 April) working hand in hand on the various elements of the project and preparing for the last year of the project. On April 10th, ClairCity held a public conference aimed at presenting results to a wider audience. The event took place at a large auditorium in the city center and was well-attended by high-level politicians, NGOs, academics, university students and school pupils. The conference included presentations from a range of local, regional and national organisations as well as ClairCity project staff. Alongside the presentations, we invited all eleven municipalities to make a poster demonstrating their local “best practices”, and this exhibition was displayed for all guests to see.

Once again the conference served to build strong and sustained relationships with the pilot city, in this case Aveiro and the other municipalities in the region. Hosted by the local project partners i.e. University of Aveiro and the CIRA (Aveiro Region Intermunicipal Community), this annual gathering was a success.

This report includes:

- A copy of the three-day programme
- An overview of participants
- References to the public relations around the conference

2 Overview of the programme

Day 1 (Monday, 8 April 2019) – Internal Project Meeting (Internal Working Day 1)

Venue:

[Aveiro University \(UAVR\) campus](#)

Room:

Carlos Borrego Auditorium at the Department of Environment and Planning (DAO)

9.00	Opening of the Day Welcome by the Vice-Rector	Hans Bolscher Artur Silva
WP update and key challenges (+ interaction with External Advisory Board)		
9.20 – 9.40	Technical Review Update: Key challenges ahead	Hans Bolscher Enda Hayes
Data Collection, Analysis and Quantification (WP3, WP5)		
9.40 – 10.10	Good practice guidelines for collecting practice-activity data (WP3) + Q&A	Olav Ten Bosch and/or Wiet Koren
10.10 – 10.40	Quantification of behaviours, baselines and scenarios (WP5) + Q&A	Kris Vanherle and Vera Rodrigues
Generating scenarios, policy analysis and Final ClairCity Policy Package (WP6, WP7)		
10.40 – 11.10	SWOT analysis and Policy Workshops results (WP6) + Q&A	Stephan Slingerland
11.10 – 11.40	Generating scenarios and Final ClairCity Policy Package (WP7) + Q&A	Svein Knudsen and/or Stephan Slingerland
11.40 – 11.50	<i>Coffee & tea break</i>	
Citizen engagement results and dissemination/exploitation of ClairCity outputs (WP2, WP4)		
11.50 -12.20	WP4 Skylines Stakeholder Dialogue Workshop and ANTS app launch: lessons learnt + Q&A	Eva Csobod
12.20 – 12.50	WP2 Communicating ClairCity / Exploiting the Results + Q&A	Laura Fogg Rogers and Svein Knudsen
12.50 – 13.10	General discussion on project's progress	
13.10 – 14.00	<i>Lunch break</i>	
Work Packages time		
14.00 – 15.30	Integrated session on preparing and implementing the Stakeholder Dialogue Workshop (WP4) and the Policy Workshop (WP6)	<i>Session by Stephan & Irati (prepared in consultation with Jo).</i>

		<p><i>Session for City Buddies and City Partners.</i></p> <p><i>Partners not involved may use this time for parallel meetings.</i></p>
15.30 – 17.00	<p>WP4-WP5-WP7 data flow session: <i>SDW results interpretation and scenario impacts</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Scenario design and report</i> • <i>Quantification of impacts</i> 	<p><i>Session by Svein Knudsen, Kris Vanherle, Vera Rodrigues.</i></p> <p><i>Session for City Buddies and City Partners.</i></p> <p><i>Partners not involved may use this time for parallel meetings.</i></p>
17.00	Surprise tour through the Aveiro Region	
19:00	Consortium dinner	

Day 2 (Tuesday 9 April 2019) – Internal Project Meeting (Internal Working Day 2)

Venue:

[Aveiro University \(UAVR\) campus](#)

Room:

Carlos Borrego Auditorium at the Environment and Planning (DAO)

9.00	Opening of the day	
ClairCity Cities / Regions – Knowledge Exchange		
9.10 – 10.10	Part I: Main lessons (positive and negative) of the ClairCity process for policy making in Bristol and Amsterdam + Q&A	Andy Edwards (BCC) Imke van Moorselaar (GGD Amsterdam) <i>Session for <u>City Buddies and City Partners</u>. Partners not involved may use this time for parallel meetings.</i>
10.10 – 10.30	<i>Coffee & tea break</i>	
10.30 – 12.00	Part II: Potential main lessons of the ClairCity process for Ljubljana, Sosnowiec, Liguria and Aveiro	Led by Stephan Slingerland (Trinomics) <i>Session for <u>City Buddies and City Partners</u> (continuation of Part I). Partners not involved may use this time for parallel meetings</i>
Looking ahead to the final year of ClairCity		
12.00 – 13.00	School competition, filming with elderly & City Day (WP4)	Eva Csobod (REC) <i>Session for <u>City Buddies and City Partners</u>. Partners not involved may use this time for parallel meetings</i>
13.00 – 14.00	<i>Lunch break</i>	
14.00 – 15.00	Communicating data - Session led by WP2 on communicating outputs and results of our work (in WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP7) visually for the next year of the project.	Laura Fogg Rogers (UWE)
15.00 – 15.20	<i>Coffee & tea break</i>	
15.20 – 16.30	Open floor: The final year of ClairCity – maximising impact, publications, dissemination, business / innovation (and preparing for the M36 Review of the Commission)	Enda Hayes (UWE) and Hans Bolscher (Trinomics) to lead. <i>It requires input from WP leaders.</i>
16.30 – 17.30	Wrapping up the 2 internal project working days	
17.30	Conference close	
19:00	Consortium dinner	

Day 3 (Wednesday, 10 April 2019) – ClairCity Annual Conference (Public Day)

Venue: Assembleia Municipal de Aveiro - Edifício da Capitania.

Address: [Av. Dr. Lourenço Peixinho, n.º 4, 3800-159 Aveiro, Portugal](#)

Registration between 9:00 and 9:30 (including simultaneous translations headset pick-up)		
9.30 – 9.40	Opening and introduction to the day	Hans Bolscher, Project Director ClairCity
Air quality in the CIRA region		
9.40 – 9.50	Welcome by the Vice-Rector of the University of Aveiro	Eduardo Anselmo Castro
9.50 – 10.00	Introduction by the President of the CIRA	José Ribau Esteves
10.00 – 10.15	Air quality in the CIRA in perspective	Alexandra Monteiro, DAO & CESAM
10.15 – 10.30	Visions for a future clean mobility in the CIRA	Susana Castelo, TISPT – Consultores em Transportes, Inovação e Sistemas, S.A.
10.30 – 10.45	Air pollution: impact on health	Isabel Lança, Administração Regional de Saúde do Centro
10.45 – 11.05	<i>Coffee & tea break {ClairCity videos with the elderly on view}</i>	
11.05 – 11.20	Role of Industry to improve on carbon and AQ	<i>Speaker t.b.c</i> PACOPAR
11.20 – 11.35	Role of the Port to improve on carbon and AQ	Maria Manuel Cruz Administração do Porto de Aveiro
11.35 – 12.20	<u>Round table 1:</u> Economic activities in relation to climate and AQ	Chaired by Carlos Borrego (UAVR) Miguel Coutinho (IDAD) António Veiga Simão (CCDR-Centro) Fernando Castro (AIDA) Ana Isabel Miranda (DAO & CESAM)
12.20 – 12.35	What's the room for cycling in the CIRA?	Trio presentation: Agostinho Oliveira (Murtosa Ciclável), José Carlos Mota (UAU-BIKE) António Rodrigues (GAFeBikeLab)
12.35 – 12.45	Price giving award best Video + showing of the video	Myriam Lopes (UAVR) and the President of the CIRA
12.45 – 14.10	<i>Lunch break {poster session CIRA municipalities; best practices} {opportunity to check out GAF-bike project across the street}</i>	
How ClairCity meets the challenge: Lessons from the project		

14.10 – 14.35	Involving citizens in policymaking - Lessons so far from ClairCity	Enda Hayes (UWE)
14.35 – 15.00	Modelling for impacts on air quality, health and carbon footprint	Vera Rodrigues (UAVR) and Kris Vanherle (TML)
15.00 – 15.25	Policy lessons from ClairCity so far	Stephan Slingerland (Trinomics)
15.25 – 15.40	<i>Coffee & tea break</i> {ClairCity videos with the elderly on view}	
15.40 – 16.40	<u>Round table 2:</u> Citizens role in AQ and Climate: behaviour and policy	<u>Chaired by</u> Jim Longhurst (UWE) Joana Ivónia (Ciclaveiro) Célia Laranjero (CM Águeda) Sérgio Lopes (Ordem dos Engenheiros)
16.40 – 16.45	Closing remarks	Hans Bolscher (Trinomics)
16.45 – 17.30	Conference close and networking drinks	
19:00	Dinner offered and hosted by José Agostinho Ribau Esteves, President of the CIRA (<i>only for ClairCity partners and the ClairCity External Advisory Board</i>)	

3 Participants

The Internal Project Working Days (April 8th & April 9th), were attended by up to 44 project partners including three members of the ClairCity External Advisory Board who joined from the UK, the Netherlands and Peru.

The public day (10th April), was attended by ClairCity project partners and over 60 external participants which included high-level politicians (including the President of the Aveiro Region and Mayor of Aveiro, and Mayors of various other municipalities in the Aveiro Region), NGOs (environmental NGOs and sustainable mobility / cycling focused NGOs), and university and school staff and students. A list of names and organisations can be found in Annex 1.

Alongside the presentations, we invited all eleven municipalities to make a poster demonstrating their local “best practices”, and this exhibition was displayed for all guests to see.

4 Public relations

Invitation to for external audiences

Figure 4-1 Save the date invitation for external audiences

ClairCity Conference

Citizen-led Air Pollution Reduction in Cities

10 April 2019
Aveiro, Portugal

ClairCity
www.claircity.eu

**Connected communities:
Improving air quality and carbon emissions
to protect public health**

We invite you to attend the ClairCity annual conference, held at the Assembleia Municipal de Aveiro, Edifício da Capitania in Aveiro, Portugal on 10 April 2019. This year the conference will focus on:

- Understanding how local and regional collaborations can tackle air pollution and carbon emissions
- Sharing best practice and cutting edge modelling and solutions

For more information visit bit.ly/aveiro2019

Communications outreach

Figure 4-2 Twitter invitation to join the conference

The conference was primarily promoted through emails to networks in the Aveiro region and more broadly in the ClairCity Associate network and other individuals and organisations following ClairCity. We used eventbrite to manage registrations and track attendees.

We also promoted the event via the ClairCity website and on Twitter, and local partners promoted the conference at events leading up to the conference.

Information around the conference is available on [this page](#) of the ClairCity website.

During the conference, twitter was used to share key points from presentations with a wider audience, being tweeted or re-tweeted by the ClairCity account. Twitter is the most relevant platform for “live-streaming” comments, and is most appropriate for the wider audience who may have wanted to follow the event.

Figure 4-3 Twitter coverage of the public presentations

5 Pictures

Internal Project Working Days

Figure 5-1 Work Package 3 presentations and discussions

Figure 5-2 Work Package 5 presenting their activities

Figure 5-3 ClairCity partners and External Advisory Board audience

Figure 5-4 Andrew Edwards from Bristol City Council presenting.

Figure 5-5 ClairCity partners and External Advisory Board audience

Public Conference

Figure 5-6 Public Conference opening session

Figure 5-7 Public conference presentation

Figure 5-8 Film competition with the elderly, award ceremony by the University of Aveiro and Mayor of Aveiro

Figure 5-9 ClairCity partners

Figure 5-10 Posters from municipalities on display during Public Conference (ClairCity named a "good practice" in various municipalities!)

Annex 1 – List of participants

1	Alves	Brenda	Universidade de Aveiro
2	Alves	Fatima	Centro Social de Oia
3	Araujo	Paulo	Camara Municipal de Oliveira do Bairro
4	Artola	Irati	Trinomics
5	Ascenso	Ana	University of Aveiro
6	Augusto	Bruno	DAO-GEMAC
7	Bak	Elof	University of Aveiro
8	Barbosa	Eduarda	Universidade de Aveiro
9	Bickel	Jon	Swisscontact
10	Bladina	Jesus	Municipio de Ilhavo
11	Bolscher	Hans	Trinomics
12	Borges	Maria	Altice Labs
9	Borrego	Carlos	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
10	Boushel	Corra	UWE Bristol
11	Cacoilo	Fernando Fidalgo	Municipio de Ilhavo
12	Campos	Marta	DAO – Internship students
13	Cardoso	José	Município de Anadia
14	Castelo	Susana	TISPT – Consultores em Transportes e Sistemas, S.A.
15	Castro	Eduardo Anselmo	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
16	Castro	Fernando	AIDA
17	Coelho	Silvia	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
18	Correia	Luís	University of Aveiro
19	Correia da Silva	Paulo Manuel	Câmara Municipal de Ovar
20	Costa	Sandra	Camara Municipal de Oliveira do Bairro

21	Costi	Patrizia	Regione Liguria
22	Cravo	Olga	CIM Região de Aveiro
23	Dunford	Chris	We The Curious
24	Dziurowicz	Natalia	Sosnowiec City Hall
25	Eduardo de Matos	José	CIM Região de Aveiro
26	Edwards	Andrew	Bristol City Council (BCC)
27	Faria	Carlos	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
28	Feio	Graça	Camara Municipal de Vagos
29	Fernandes	Patricia	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
30	Ferreira	Joana	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
31	Ferreira	Nuno	Município de Albergaria-a-Velha
32	Fogg-Rogers	Laura	UWE Bristol
33	Goncalves	Pedro	PACOPAR
34	Guedes	Antonio	Município sever do Vouga
35	Hayes	Enda	UWE Bristol
36	Henriques	Elisabete	Município de Sever do Vouga
37	Homem	Catarina	Município de Anadia
38	Ivonia	Joana	Ciclaveiro
39	Jameinos	Helena	CCDRC
40	Kewo	Angreine	Denmark Technical University (DTU)
41	Knudsen	Svein	Norwegian Institute for Air Research (NILU)
42	Koren	Wiet	Statistics Netherlands
43	Kossowska-Siwiec	Barbara	Sosnowiec City Hall
44	Lanca	Isabel	Administracao Regional de Saude do Centro
45	Laranjeira	Celia	Município Águeda
46	Leandro	Antonio	Município de Ilhavo

47	Longhurst	James	UWE Bristol
48	Lopes	Myriam	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
49	Malheiro	Salvador	Municipio de Ovar
50	Miranda	Ana	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
51	Monteiro	Alexandra	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
52	Mota	Jose Carlos	UAU-BIKE
53	Mourao	Nino	DAO – Internship students
54	Novo	Duarte	Camara Municipal de Oliveira do Bairro
55	Nunes	Teresa	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
56	Oktawirani	Panka	University of Jember
57	Oliveira	Kevin	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
58	Oliveira	Agostinho	Municipio de Murtosa
59	Pacheco	Teresa	Escala Gafanha da Nazare
60	Papics	Peter	Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML)
61	Pato	Jorge	Camara Municipal de Oliveira do Bairro
62	Patrone	Angela Teresa	Regione Liguria
63	Pintado	Lino	Municipio de Anadia
64	Popit	Sabina	City of Ljubljana
65	Rabaça	Luis Manuel	Câmara Municipal de Ílhavo
66	Rafael	Sandra	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
67	Ramos	Manuel	Retired (participant of film competition)
68	Regalado	Ricardo	Centro Social de Oia
69	Regalado	Silveiro Rodrigues	Municipio de Vagos
70	Reis	Johnny	Universidade de Aveiro
71	Relvas	Helder	University of Aveiro
72	Ribau Esteves	José	CIRA
73	Rocha	Bruno	Município de Vagos

74	Rocha	Rita	Câmara Municipal de Vagos
75	Rodrigues	Vera	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
76	Rodrigues	Antonio	GAFeBikeLab
77	Rodrigues	Paulo	PS Aveiro CMA
78	Rosa	Tomas	CIRA
79	Rosado	Isabel	Câmara Municipal de Vagos
80	Sabina	Diamantino Manuel	Município de Estarreja
81	Santos	Diogo Almeida	PACOPAR
82	Seabra	Cristina	CCRDR
83	Seixas	Vânia	University of Aveiro (UAVR)
84	Seixas	Jose	Programa Idade Maior
85	-	-	Caretaker Jose Seixas
86	Silva	Paula	Município de Estarreja
87	Silva	Marcelo	DAO - Universidade de Aveiro
88	Silva	Ana	Município de Sevr do Vouga
89	Silva	Egídio	Independente
90	Silva	Afonso	University of Aveiro (CESAM)
91	Silva	Angela	Centro Social de Oia
92	Slingerland	Stephan	Trinomics
93	Soares	Joana	Norwegian Institute for Air Research (NILU)
94	Soares	Bruno	Município de Ilhavo
95	Student 1		Escala Gafanha de Nazare
96	Student 2		Escala Gafanha de Nazare
97	Student 3		Escala Gafanha de Nazare
98	Student 4		Escala Gafanha de Nazare
99	ten Bosch	Olav	Statistics Netherlands
100	Trozzi	Carlo	Techne Consulting

101	Vaccaro	Rita	Techne Consulting
102	Vanherle	Kris	Transport & Mobility Leuven (TML)
103	Vieira	Joana Filipa	Universidade de Aveiro